

Case Study: Energy Project in Mexico

An energy extraction project in Mexico requires \$150m initial capital expenditure and will generate annual returns of \$27.5m/yr for 10 years. Interest rates on the Mexican “peso” have averaged around 5.5 per cent over the past decade. However, the risk-adjusted “opportunity cost of capital” in Mexico has been on a rising trend, reaching 7.75 per cent this year as minimum attractive return for investors. This is mainly due to USMCA replacing NAFTA following the US Administration mandates on trade restrictions and strict border control.

Exhibit 1: Mexico Energy Fields

The Mexican government subsidizes energy to the average citizen, equivalent to a subsidy rate of 39%. The subsidized local price is sold at \$65 per unit, whereas the international FOB export price is \$112 per unit, and the Cif import price is \$118 per unit. The project’s main target is local citizen consumption with no expected export proceeds. However, in this type of energy projects, a common sustainability criterion entails that annual project returns to society are financial returns multiplied by the ratio between the opportunity cost of energy extraction and the true economic cost of utilizing this energy resource.

Exhibit 2: Mexican Agricultural *Ejid*os System

With LIBOR at 0.962 %/yr on the British pound and 2.78%/yr on the US dollar, Mexico has a country risk factor of 3 out of 7 based on OECD country risk classification.

The official exchange rate for Mexico's "peso" currency is 19.08 pesos per US\$. However, some international experts say that the true floating exchange rate is different, due to Central Bank interventions towards an overly depreciated currency in order to enhance Mexico's exports to the world market. In contrast, other experts mention that the peso currency is actually over-appreciated due to internal politics to contain inflation and achieve a decent standard of living for the average Mexican citizen. Mexico's BOP (Balance of Payments) has the following data: \$39,177 million for exports, \$40,764 million for imports, and \$24 million for the country's net capital account deficit, with capital inflows at their lowest level of \$551 million this year.

The project will employ 112 workers directly. Induced jobs have an employment multiplier factor of 8, and the informal sector in Mexico is approximately 15% of the economy. Within the Mexican energy sector, temporary jobs are estimated at around 20%.

Exhibit 3: Mexico's National Flag

Green symbolizes independence. White symbolizes the purity of a religious society, mostly Roman Catholic religion. Red symbolizes sacrifice of all lost lives for the country's sake. In the middle of the flag is the Mexican coat of arms (Escudo Nacional de México) which is an eagle biting a snake, while it is standing on a cactus growing out of rocks in the middle of water. It has the eagle as a symbol of noble victory over the evil serpent snake, while such victory is grounded on the country's land resources of water and greenery.

Mexico's President signed a new Parliament law which raises the minimum wage to 88.36 pesos per day, equivalent to 28,275 pesos per year. This law has been effective since Dec 1, 2017. The World Factbook reports that Mexico's GDP composition by sector is 3.9% agriculture, 31.6% industry, and 64% services. On the other hand, Mexico's GDP composition by employment is 13.4% agriculture, 24.1% industry, and 61.9% services. Mexico's energy projects are classified as part of the "industrial sector" according to the National Institute for Statistics and Geography (INEGI).

Although Mexico's unemployment is roughly below 4%, yet the poverty rate is as high as 46% nationwide. The average income (adjusted PPP GDP per capita) is \$19,500 per year which is considered a good estimate for the economic value of average productivity of a typical Mexican worker.

As is common in many developing countries, Mexico's traditional sector has been agriculture. Historically, Mexico has been famous for specialized farming, with special focus on corn as a national crop harvest. The *Ejidors* peasant system has been a Mexican cultural tradition whereby community members individually farm designated parcels and collectively maintain communal holdings.

Notes:

This case study predominantly uses actual country data for Mexico. However, some data has been extrapolated and further assumptions have been made to simplify the analysis. This case study has used country information obtained from the following sources:

- (1) Trading Economics (Mexico): <https://tradingeconomics.com/mexico/indicators>
- (2) LIBOR Global Rates: <http://www.global-rates.com/interest-rates/libor/libor.aspx>
- (3) OECD Country Risk Classifications: <http://www.oecd.org/trade/xcred/cre-crc-current-english.pdf>
- (4) World Bank (Country Profile: Mexico): <https://data.worldbank.org/country/mexico>
- (5) World Factbook: <https://www.cia.gov/library/publications/the-world-factbook/>
- (6) INEGI (Mexico National Institute for Statistics and Geography): <http://en.www.inegi.org.mx>

Open Class Discussion on the Case:

Synopsis: Mexico's Energy Sector- Economic Feasibility and Spill-Over Effects

An energy project in Mexico is forecasted to generate needed electricity and power generation for Mexican industrialization efforts. Yet, the energy project is expected to greatly displace agricultural corn harvests in multiple traditional Mexican villages. Within the project feasibility study, a careful review of the benefits and costs of this project is needed, using economic and spill-over effects, for the project to pass the feasibility test and get needed state approvals.

Theme: Energy is strategically desirable for electricity and power generation and will have highly significant impacts on industrialization with technology spill-over effects to other sectors of the Mexican economy. However, the energy field locations are on agricultural corn fields which are also strategically important for food consumption of the population.

Discuss the following:

- A. What are the positive economic impacts of energy project in Mexico?
- B. What are the negative economic impacts of energy project in Mexico?
- C. How can we ensure that the project's economic benefits exceed economic costs?

Note: A & B in Session 1, and C in Session 2.

Technical Questions (below) for Session 3.

Technical Questions:

1. Calculate the financial NPV of this energy project using the 7.75%/year risk-adjusted interest rate given in the case.
2. What is the true economic cost of energy in Mexico after incorporating the subsidy? Compare to local price paid by Mexican households.
3. What is the shadow price of energy in Mexico? In this project, is energy an “exportable” commodity or an “importable” commodity? Explain.
4. What is the shadow discount rate (SDR) for Mexico?
5. Is SDR much lower than MARR? If so, explain the economic significance of this fact.
6. Calculate the economic NPV for this project. Use shadow pricing with the economic adjustment for “common sustainability criterion” mentioned in the case (at the end of the second paragraph), and the social discount rate. Compare to financial NPV.
7. What is the shadow exchange rate (SER) for Mexico? Compare to the official 19.08 pesos per US dollar. Is the Mexican currency over-depreciated or over-appreciated? Explain.
8. What is the minimum wage in Mexico in US dollars using SER? Compare to the PPP GDP per capita.
9. Using the VMP and Relative Productivity Index (given below), calculate the wage rate for skilled employees working in the energy sector. By similar method, calculate the wage rate for the unskilled workers and compare to the minimum wage. Do the unskilled workers in Mexico deserve to have a minimum wage? To what degree? Explain.
$$\text{VMP} = (\text{Relative Productivity Index}) \times (\text{PPP GDP per capita})$$

with *Relative Productivity Index* = (% of GDP / % of Employment) by sector.
10. Estimate the total employment generation of this project with employment multiplier effects. The total employment generation should include direct, indirect, induced, temporary, and informal jobs.